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4 Emerging risks along Arctic coastlines

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11 Nearly one-third of the global shoreline is in the Arctic, a region undergoing some of the most
12 rapid warming and substantial environmental transitions due to climate change. While Arctic
13 research has largely focused on terrestrial and open-ocean systems, there is now an urgent need
14 to focus on the unique challenges associated with changing coastal ecosystems.

15

16 Global climate change is a pervasive threat to species and ecosystems, with significant
17 economic, societal, and ecological consequences. The Arctic is a hotspot of change, with
18 temperatures increasing three to seven times faster than the global average¹, and striking
19 impacts of climate change are already evident in the region. The Arctic tundra is greening,
20 permafrost coastlines are eroding, and climate models predict that the Arctic Ocean may
21 become consistently ice-free in September as early as 2035². Warming temperatures are
22 inducing species to shift northward, both on land and in the ocean, as new habitats become
23 available. While this promotes the spread and abundance of boreal species in the Arctic,
24 warming and diminishing sea ice threaten iconic Arctic marine species. Critical walrus haul-

25 out habitats are disappearing, and polar bears are being forced onto land, where prolonged
26 fasting leads to reduced reproduction and survival.

27 The high-impact transition from a white to a blue Arctic Ocean, greening landscape, and broad
28 borealization has sparked growing interest in understanding the ecosystem-wide consequences
29 of warming. Research examining climate change impacts on Arctic terrestrial and open-ocean
30 ecosystems has produced projections of future environmental changes and developed
31 ecological models, based on broad environmental parameters, such as, nutrients, temperature,
32 or sea ice dynamics (e.g., ice extent or duration), to forecast climate-driven impacts across
33 systems. Although model predictions may hold true for terrestrial and open-ocean realms, they
34 likely fail to capture patterns in coastal ecosystems. Coastal ecosystems are shaped by a
35 complex mosaic of physical and chemical conditions, including drivers of terrestrial origin. If
36 coastal-specific environmental parameters are omitted, the resulting model predictions may not
37 align with observed occurrences, leading to strong prediction–observation discrepancies.
38 Currently, there are substantial gaps in our understanding of how coastal drivers affect the
39 distribution of shallow water species, limiting our ability to fully comprehend and predict the
40 impacts of rapid climate change. This is particularly concerning for coastal ecosystems along
41 the Arctic permafrost coastline, which accounts for approximately one-third of the global total
42 and is undergoing particularly high rates of change, yet remains systematically understudied^{3,4}.

43

44 Arctic coastal waters are of immense importance, providing a range of ecosystem services
45 including nursery habitats for fish, remineralization, carbon sequestration, and coastal
46 protection. In the Arctic, coastal areas also serve as feeding grounds for whales and keystone
47 predators like seals and Arctic Char, offering access to rich benthic and pelagic food resources.
48 Furthermore, Arctic coastal fisheries are important national exports, and healthy ecosystems

49 are important to the millions of coastal inhabitants who rely on them for food security, as well
50 as for the cultural and social identity connected to the coastal environment.

51

52 **Emerging climate risks**

53 It is becoming increasingly evident that the cumulative pressure from complex interactions
54 among various environmental conditions in the coastal zone can, at least locally, exceed that of
55 terrestrial and open ocean systems⁵. Global-scale processes – such as warming, sea level rise,
56 and coastal erosion – interact with local environmental drivers like freshwater runoff, creating
57 areas with abrupt environmental changes (Fig. 1). This, in turn, can reduce organism fitness
58 and survival, alter community composition, and affect ecosystem functioning and productivity.
59 Here, I present examples of unique climate-change-driven changes in Arctic coastal systems,
60 their potential to impact species, and highlight the urgent need to strengthen international
61 research efforts within these topics to better understand their impacts and global implications.

62

63 *Glacial retreat*

64 Retreating glaciers are creating new coastlines as marine-terminating glaciers withdraw. These
65 newly exposed paraglacial zones may provide novel habitats for coastal and intertidal species.
66 The paraglacial zones are, however, highly dynamic and characterized by rapid
67 geomorphological changes and high sediment fluxes⁶. Sea-level rise associated with glacial
68 melt can further result in habitat loss through coastal squeeze or submergence of entire habitat
69 types, such as rocky shores, potentially reducing the availability and suitability of novel coastal
70 habitats (Fig. 1). Understanding these processes in tandem is essential for predicting
71 biodiversity responses.

72

73 *The melting ice foot*

74 In the Arctic, intertidal air temperatures can vary by more than 60°C annually⁷, potentially
75 subjecting resident species (such as mussels, barnacles, and canopy-forming algae) to extreme
76 temperature stress when emerged at low tides. Extreme low temperatures partly determine
77 species' poleward distribution limits and act as a barrier to range expansions. Microhabitats are
78 known to mitigate these effects by providing a thermal refuge, increasing biodiversity, and
79 biomass. In suitable habitats, Arctic community richness and biomass can be comparable to
80 those of lower latitudes⁸. A unique Arctic microhabitat is the so-called "ice foot" – sea ice that
81 is attached to the hard substratum on the shore (Fig. 2a-b). Underneath the ice, organisms are
82 sheltered from extreme air temperatures. However, the ice foot is melting earlier, increasing
83 the risks of exposing organisms to cold snaps in late spring. Exposure to detrimental cold snaps
84 could result in widespread mortality of intertidal populations, similar to the catastrophic effects
85 of heatwaves at lower latitudes⁹. Thus, counterintuitively, Arctic warming could increase
86 freeze-induced mortality in intertidal species, reducing abundance and biodiversity (Fig. 1).

87

88 *Ice scour*

89 The macrobenthic species richness in Arctic fjords can exceed 800, but varies markedly across
90 the region¹⁰. Increased glacier ice export raises the risk of ice scour caused by floating ice
91 scraping the shoreline and seabed, which is highly destructive to subsea infrastructure and kills
92 up to 99% of affected organisms (Fig. 2c-d)¹¹. However, ice scour impacts may represent a
93 transformative stage. As continuous melt retracts glaciers on land, the supply of icebergs
94 diminishes, leading to a decline in ice scour, releasing the stress of ice scour (Fig. 2). Thus, this
95 climate risk may follow a bell-shaped trajectory, with current and near-future increases in ice
96 scour followed by a gradual reduction. Understanding this conundrum in temporal progression
97 is crucial for forecasting coastal ecosystem responses

98

99 *Freshening and Coastal darkening*

100 The runoff from the Greenland Ice Sheet has increased sixfold since the 1970's¹², exporting
101 large amounts of meltwater and sediments to the surrounding coastal areas. Seasonal variation
102 in meltwater discharge determines the salinity of fjords and straits, with salinity near river
103 mouths and glacial discharges dropping below 5, depending on season and water conditions.
104 Prolonged and unpredictable exposure to lowered salinities increases susceptibility to
105 temperature stress and reduces survival of benthic species, including foundation species, whose
106 loss can disrupt fundamental ecological processes and alter the dynamics of the ecosystem. As
107 glaciers become land-terminating, river run-off increases, enriching coastal waters with
108 inorganic suspended matter, which causes coastal darkening as turbidity in the surface waters
109 increases (Fig. 2 e-f). Reduced light availability diminishes the abundance of benthic habitat-
110 forming macroalgal species (Fig. 1) and decreases pelagic primary productivity, potentially
111 outweighing the facilitative effect of an increased open water period on primary production,
112 which could ultimately shift community metabolism from autotrophic to heterotrophy¹³.

113

114 *Coastal stratification, acidification, and oligotrophication*

115 Runoff from land-terminating glaciers can enhance water stratification and reduce alkalinity,
116 weakening the ability of coastal waters to buffer pH changes. Increased freshwater input dilutes
117 naturally occurring alkalinity, reducing the capacity of surface water to neutralize ocean
118 acidification. Stratification further acts as a barrier to vertical mixing, limiting the exchange of
119 heat, oxygen, and nutrients, and preventing deeper, more alkaline waters from replenishing the
120 surface layer. As a result, surface waters in some Arctic fjords have already shown signs of
121 being undersaturated with respect to calcium carbonate¹⁴, which marine shell-formers rely on
122 to build and maintain their shells. The accompanying decrease in pH can also reduce the
123 thermal tolerance of benthic invertebrates, increasing their vulnerability to temperature stress.

124 Compounding these effects, terrestrial greening can intensify nutrient limitation in fjords by
125 reducing nitrate export from land, as expanding vegetation retains more nitrogen in biomass.
126 Terrestrial nitrate can contribute nearly half of a fjord's nitrate pool¹⁵, and this decline in
127 nutrient supply may contribute to a drop in primary production, signaling a potential climate
128 change impact where both chemical buffering and biological productivity are progressively
129 undermined.

130

131 **Understanding coastal change**

132 Knowledge of the Arctic coastal zone remains limited, but evidence suggests that the
133 intensifying climate change is triggering dramatic biological changes. To understand the
134 multifaceted impacts across all levels of biological organization, from species-specific
135 responses to system-wide tipping points, increased coordination of research across the Arctic
136 region is necessary. Accurate pan-Arctic predictions of change require broadening the
137 spatiotemporal coverage of sampling sites and long-term monitoring programs. Standardized
138 experiments and observations across Arctic nations are necessary to detect commonalities in
139 climate change responses across different coastlines. Importantly, research efforts should
140 include local communities and Indigenous knowledge, as they provide unique perspectives and
141 context-specific insights. Although the combination of complex environmental interactions and
142 variability in coastal topography and ocean currents makes coastal ecological predictions
143 inherently challenging, the impacts of climate change in conjunction with other processes are
144 essential to understand the species-to ecosystem-wide risks.

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152 **Competing interests**

153 The author declares no competing interests

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155 **Figures:**

156 **Figure 1:** Conceptual diagrams of emerging climate risks in Arctic coastal systems. The
157 transition from a present white (left) to future blue and green (right) Arctic. As land-based
158 glaciers retreat, sea level rises, leading to coastal squeeze, where coastal habitats are lost due
159 to limited space (a). The loss of the protective ice foot covering the intertidal zone raises the
160 risk of exposure to detrimental sub-zero air temperatures (b). Ice scour caused by floating ice
161 removes up to 99% of organisms. Ice scour intensity will decrease as glaciers retreat on land,
162 potentially increasing benthic biomass and biodiversity (c). River runoff exports sediments,
163 reducing water clarity and limiting primary production and the depth distribution of benthic
164 algal species (d), causes stratification and decreased pH in coastal waters (e)

165

166 **Figure 2:** An ice foot covering the entire vertical extent of the intertidal zone, sheltering
167 organisms from extreme air temperatures (a) (photo: Jakob Thyrring). Intertidal species
168 exposed as the ice foot has retracted (b) (photo: Jakob Thyrring). Macroalgal-covered rocky
169 shoreline in a fjord without ice scour (c) (photo: Mikael K. Sejr), and a barren shoreline exposed
170 to drifting ice (d) (photo: Jakob Thyrring). Clean surface water in a fjord with marine-

171 terminating glaciers (e) (photo: Jakob Thyrring), and a large plume of sediment in a fjord with
172 a land-terminating glacier where meltwater is received from rivers (f) (photo: Rui Selbra).

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